

THE IMPACT OF CAPITAL STRUCTURE ON FIRMS PERFORMANCE IN NIGERIA: DOES INDUSTRY HETEROGENEOUS FACTORS COUNT?

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Abstract: This study was conducted to examine the impact of Capital structure on firms' value within the influence of heterogeneous factors such as firm-specific, industry-specific and country-specific factors. The study employed a sample of eighteen (18) firms from nine (9) sectors of the Nigerian economy. The study covered a period of ten (10) years (2012- 2022) and adopted panel data analysis while using random and fixed effect models in estimation. The dependent variable for this study is Tobin's Q which serves as a proxy for firms' value while the independent variables are long term debt, equity capital, interest expense, firm size and firm Age. The study found out that a firm's market value is positively and significantly influenced by its choice of capital structure; capital structure also changes given industry heterogeneity. This study concludes that since we have many theories on capital structure, firms should have financial policy on the type of capital structure they intend to adopt based on the prevailing circumstances. The study therefore, recommended that firms should ensure that the proportion of leverage to equity do not grow to unsustainable levels to avoid the result of diminishing effect on firm value.

Keywords: Capital structure, Tobin's Q, Firm value, Equity, Firm size and Firm Age

Introduction

Firms are usually confronted with many financial decisions that require funding. These decisions include Dividend decision, Liquidity decision, Investment and financial decision. Firms have many capital structure alternatives they use to fund their business operations. The capital structure available to firms include long-term debt, specific short-term debt, common equity, debt-equity mix, preferred equity and retained earnings. Firms face decision problem of which source of finance to use in its business operations to maximize the values of their firm. This issue of using the appropriate capital structure to obtain the best firm value gave rise in Modigliani and Millier (1958) seminal article on the issue of relationship between a firm's choice of finance and its value. Most often, firms adopt different capital structure decisions best known to them. Some firms may decide to go into competition and this refers to the extent to which certain firms in the industry dominate the entire market. This type of firm is monopolistic in nature and can go extra mile to leverage on its capital which might affect its firm value. Again, firms with high physical technology incur high fixed cost and this can impact on its capital structure and firm's value. Firm's value is not only determined by capital structure alone, but by imperfect market condition factors group under firm-specific, industry specific and country-specific such

as firm size, profitability, corporate tax, bankruptcy costs, industry type, and internal policies influence the capital structure decision of a firm (Akeem, Edwin, Kiyanjui and Kayode , 2014).

Firm's choice of capital structure and the effect of industry heterogeneous factors on the firm's value have given rise to debates and postulation of theories in support or against one form of capital structure or the other and even disputing the fact that capital structure alone does not impact on firm's value. This position has generated argument and literatures on what actually impacts on firm's value. However, adopting an appropriate capital structure that is sustainable and improves stakeholder's wealth cannot be over emphasized. Many firms have collapsed resulting from the use of wrong capital structure, hence, such situation should be prevented by proper information of capital mix. Capital structure is of serious importance as it plays a phenomenal role in assisting firms to achieve the goals of their stakeholders. According to Riahibelkaonni (1999), capital structure includes different kinds of equities and liabilities, stating the proportions of the debt equity mix. Depending on the mix, a firm can be classified as levered or unlevered. It is very important to apply caution to the use of debts even when debts offer tax deductibility advantage as the interest to be repaid is not taxed, essentially reducing the overall cost of capital (Krishnan and Moyer, 1997). However, this doesn't go indefinitely as the costs associated with debt financing increases as the level of leverage increases. Therefore, the firm has to ensure that the debt-equity mix it utilizes must be one that gives optimal or near optimal satisfaction to its shareholders.

Finding the best mix of financing resources that will maximize return without affecting shareholders' interest is known as capital structure decision (Fatoki, Wafula &Waweru, 2021). A firm's capital structure is very important in ascertaining the long-run survival and sustainability of firms. The capital structure refers to a company's overall sources of funding which can range from retained earnings to stock and debt financing. Rodionova and Samuel (2019) noted that capital structure, according to agency cost theory can influence firm's value positively or negatively. According to Chadha & Sharma (2015), capital structure decision is a continuous process, whether the firm requires funding for the project. Therefore, striking a balance between the risks and returns in firm's operation is the purpose of capital structure.

This study joins the debates and the plethora of studies on how firms financing mix (capital structure) impact on firm's performance by investigating the influence of industry heterogeneity on the linkage between capital structure and firm's value. Brigham and Houston (2007) assert that the operations of firms in a particular industry differ from that of another. For example, firms operating under different industries have different fixed cost and this is expected to shape their capital structure. According to Li and Islam (2019), factors like competition, technology, growth opportunities and operating strategies can influence the financing need of these firms and by extension, their capital structure. Not until recently, only few studies have empirically investigated the link between capital structure and firm value between industries. Recent studies like that carried out by Al-slehat (2020), Ishari (2016), Jeleel and Olayiwola (2017) and Igbal (2018) have investigated the impact of capital structure on specific industries. Findings have shown varying results vis-à-vis negative, positive and in some cases no relationship. Thus, this study intends to examine the role of industry heterogeneity in moderating the relationship between capital structure and firm values among fifteen (15) companies selected from two sectors (conglomerates and consumer goods) of quoted companies on the Nigeria Stock Exchange.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Determining capital structure of a firm has been a difficult task to do because of many factors under consideration. Firms raise finances for their businesses through long-term debt, specific short-term debt, common equity, debt-equity mix, preferred equity and retained earnings. Since firms operate under different industries, they have different fixed costs that demand different capital structures. Most importantly, some firms go into competition to take a market as a monopoly and this ambition will require a change in capital structure. Some firm's will equally adopt technologies that will require high leverage for its operation. In view of the firms' and industry heterogeneous factors, it becomes difficult to determine what should be the capital structure of a firm. The lack of a precise methodology to determine a firm's optimal capital structure that will boost productivity, profitability, growth, stakeholder satisfaction, firm value, minimizes cost and strike a balance between risk and return is the major problem of this study and has generated a lot of mixed results in the literature.

No single theory has sufficiently explained the capital structure effect on firm performance. Firm's have a diverse level of leverage, the determination of the best mix to enhance performance by managers remains a puzzle to be solved in corporate finance theory and finance literature. However, it is difficult to determine the optimal structure because the financing decision of firms vary according to the rate of risk rated to each financing option as well as the relationship between risk and return (Abu-Rub, et al, 2012).

Many studies have been carried out on this topic. Ogbulu and Emeni (2012) reported irrelevance of equity capital to firm value using debt and equity as independent variables. Antwi et al (2012), reported relevance of equity capital to firm value using same variables. Since they used the same variables but observed difficult results, there is need for further research on the topic. This study tries to find out the reason for the differences in the result by introducing in the model industry factor of firm size and firm age. Ogbulu and Emeni (2012) used 124 quoted companies in Nigeria stock exchange. Antwi et al (2012) used all 34 quoted companies in Ghana Stock Exchange. This study uses quoted firms in two sectors of Nigeria stock exchange.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study was to examine the impact of capital structure and the influence of industry heterogeneous factors on firms' performance. The specific objectives include to examine the impact of long-term-debt (leverage) on firms' value, ascertain the effect of common equity on firms' value and to assess the influence of industry-specific factors (firm size and firm Age) on firms' value.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Capital Structure

The term capital structure according to Kennon (2010) refers to the percentage of capital (money) at work in a business by type. It is company's use of varied funding sources to finance operations and growth. There are two forms of capital: equity capital and debt capital. Alfred (2007) states that firm's capital structure is the proportion of debt and equity in the total capital structure of the firm. Pandey (1999) in the work of Adeyemi and Oboh (2011) differentiated between capital structure and financial structure by affirming that the various

means used to raise funds represent the firm's financial structure, while the capital structure represents the proportionate relationship between long-term debt and equity capital.

Therefore, a firm's capital structure is described as the capital mix of both equity and long term debt in financing its assets. Since capital structure has been perceived to influence firm's value, firms must then decide the equity-debt mix that maximizes firm's value. The selection of optimal capital structure is an important strategic financial decision for every finance manager. A capital structure that reduces cost and maximizes firm's value is what has been termed an "optimal capital structure" An optimal capital structure can be said to have been achieved when the weighted average cost of capital (WACC) is at its minimum (Udobi – Owoloja et al, 2020).

2.1.2 Firm Value

According to Lawal (2014), firm value is the net worth of a firm at a given period of time. In the event of a takeover or merger, the firm's value is what is considered and not its performance, since the former shows the current net worth of the firm. Susanti and Restina (2018) view firm's value to be the perception of investors about firms that are often associated with stock. Hoque, Hossain and Hassain (2014) assert that firm value and Investor's confidence have a positive relationship, implying that as firm value increases investor overall confidence is increased. According to Ehrhard and Bringham (2003), the value of a business based on the going concern expectation is the present value of all the expected future cash flows to be generated by the assets, discounted at the company's weighted average cost of capital (WACC). From this, it can be seen that the WACC has a direct effect on the value of a business (Johannes and Dhanraj, 2007). WACC is used to define a firm's value by discounting future cash flows. Minimizing WACC of any firm will maximize the value of the firm (Antwi, Mills, and Zhao, 2012).

2.1.3 Firm/Industry Specific Factors and Capital Structure – Firm value nexus

The kind of capital structure adopted by firms has been modeled to be a function of some industry specific factors to include competition growth opportunities, technology, capital, risk and operating cost (Vatavu, et al, 2015), growth potential or future investment opportunity (Myers, 1984), Dividend policy (Miller and Modigliani, 1961, Gordon, 1967); the size of a firm (Gordon, 1962).

According to Scott and Martin (1975), financial needs of firms vary across industries, and the study found differing degree of financial leverage between mining and aerospace industries. Mackay and Philips (2005) assert that the difference in capital structures can be attributed to the use of different level of technology and risk adopted by the firm. Similarly, Miao (2005) found that companies that operate in industries with high growth in technology, high solvency and fixed cost used lesser debt. According to Li and Islam (2019), factors peculiar to industries can significantly utter the capital structure of firms. Economic characteristics and competitive dynamics can influence the operating strategies of firms (Wahlen, et al, 2011). We can also note that firms in industries with incentive competition are associated with low profitability, therefore, less leveraged. In addition, it is also logical that firms that operate in industries having high growth in technology will have a very low fixed cost and by extension low leverage. However, industries with low growth opportunities (industries with matured firms) will have a positive relationship with leverage.

2.1.4 Long Term Debt and Firm Value

According to Adeyemi and Oboh, (2011), debt capital in a firm's capital structure refers to the long-term bonds the firm use in financing its investment decisions because the firm has years, if not decades, to come up with the principal, while paying interest only in the meantime. The cost of debt capital in the capital structure depends on the health of the firm's balance sheet.

2.1.5 Equity Capital

Pandey (1999) defined equity capital as including share-capital, share premium, reserves and surpluses (retained earnings). Typically, equity capital consists of two types which include: contributed capital, which is the money that was originally invested in the business in exchange for shares of stock or ownership and retained earnings, which represents profits from past years that have been kept by the company and used to strengthen the balance sheet or fund growth, acquisition or for expansion.

2.1.6 The Firm Size

Firm size plays a vital role in capital structure decision making process. Many studies point out that a firm size plays an important role in the determination of firm performance. Beck et al (2005) argue that firm size has a strong association with firm's survival, profitability and productivity, though, depending on policy implementation, legal, financial policy effects and their size. Large size firms tend to diversify and benefit from economy of scale. Raja & Kumar (2005) posit that firm size exhibit a positive relation with the performance of listed firms.

2.1.7 The Firm Age

The Firm Age is associated with years of business experience, expertise and reduction in perceived risks (Mahajan & Singh, 2013). Since old firms are expected to have large market shares, high clientele patronage, customer loyalty, well established logistic channels, hence, they are better disposed to operational strategies in producing various goods/services to meet various customers' demands. However, Graham et al, (2011) posit that young firms tend to be prone to distress during unfavorable business period. Carroll (2003) observes that young firm is prone to failure because of diversion of their resources to establish internal routines, developing credible exchange relationship and training of the employees.

2.2 Conceptual Model

It is observed that the essential argument in the capital structure decision is how to strike a balance between risk and return to attain optimum capital structure. However, the existence of an optimum capital structure has not been accepted by all, but there are a lot of empirical evidences and propositions that accepted the existence of optimum capital structure (Wippen, 1966 and Ozkan, 2001). Based on the various concepts associated with corporate capital structure, this study adopted a model developed by Lambe Isaac (2014) in which he presented a firm's financing decision process as in figure 2.1.

Fig. 2.1: A firm's financing decision process
Culled from Lambe (2014).

A firm's finance function consists of four (4) major decisions which include: the dividend decision, the liquidity decision, the investment decision and the financing decision. A firm makes these decisions simultaneously and continually in the normal course of its business operations. Though they do not have to occur in the sequence, but are interrelated with one another. When a firm is making one of the decisions, it is at the same time making another decision. After a firm has taken these decisions to the point of financing them especially the investment decision, it then decides on its capital structure to best finance its investment decisions.

In determining the optimal capital structure of a firm, the firm has to properly evaluate the likely effects of such a decision on both its risk and return, that is, how the firm can maximize its returns and at the same time minimizing its risks. It is by these evaluations that the firm is able to strike a balance between its risks and return in order to arrive at an optimal capital structure which maximizes its market value. It should be noted that a firm's choice of capital structure is geared towards maximizing its return and minimizing its risks in order to attain an optimal market value as seen in figure 2.1

2.3 Theoretical Review

There have been substantial research efforts by different scholars in determining what seems to be an optimal capital structures for firms, yet there is no universally accepted theory throughout the literatures explaining the debt-equity choice for firms. However, several theories have emerged explaining firms' capital structure and the resultant effect on their market values. Among these theories that will be discussed include the Pecking order theory, the Agency cost theory, the Modigliani and Miller theory and the Static Trade-off theory.

2.3.1 The Pecking order theory

The Pecking order theory of capital structure as introduced by Donaldson (1961) is among the most influential theories of corporate leverage. It goes contrary to the idea of firms having a unique combination of debt and equity finance which minimize their cost of capital. The theory suggests that when a firm is looking for ways to finance its long-term investment, it has a well-defined order of preference with respect to the sources of finance it uses. It states that a firm's first preference should be the utilization of internal funds (i.e. retain earnings), followed by debt and then external equity. He argues that the more profitable the firms become, the lesser they borrow because they would have sufficient internal finance to undertake their investment projects. He further argues that it is when the internal finance is inadequate that a firm should source for external finance and most preferably, bank borrowings or corporate bonds. And after exhausting both internal and bank borrowing and corporate bonds, the final and least preferred source of finance is to issue new equity capital. Pecking Order theory tries to capture the costs of asymmetric information which states that companies prioritize their sources of financing (from internal financing to equity) according to the principle of least effort, or of least resistance, preferring to raise equity as a financing means of last resort. Hence, internal funds are used first, and when that is exhausted, debt is issued, and when it is not sensible to issue any more debt, equity is issued.

To avoid the problem arising from information asymmetry, firms usually fulfill their financing needs by preferring retained earnings as their main source of financing, followed by debt and finally external equity financing as the last resort. This work is anchored on pecking order theory of capital structure because the theory is realistic and orderly in raising sustainable funds for business growth.

2.3.2 Modigliani & Miller Theory

Modigliani and Miller (1958), promulgated a theory that asserts the irrelevance and of no impact of capital structure on firm's value under certain assumptions. These assumptions include the absence of taxes, presence of information asymmetry, no transaction or bankruptcy cost. According to the theory, the weighted cost of capital (WACC) is unchanged given changes in capital structure. Hence, the value of the firm is determined not by the capital structure but by the efficient use of firm's assets and free cash flow discounted with related rate of return. However, this theory does not meet real life conditions and has prompted other theories aiming to ascertain the relevance of capital structure to firm's value.

2.3.3 The Agency cost theory

The Agency cost theory of capital structure as propounded by Jensen and Meckling (1976) states that an optimal capital structure will be determined by minimizing the costs arising from conflicts between the parties involved. They argued that agency costs play an important role in financing decisions due to the conflict that may exist between shareholders and debt holders. And that when companies are approaching financial distress, shareholders can encourage management to take decisions, which in effect, expropriate funds from debt holders. The general result of these extensions is that the combination of leverage related costs (such as bankruptcy and agency costs) and a tax advantage of debt produces an optimal capital structure at less than a 100 percent debt financing as the tax advantage is traded off against the likelihood of incurring the costs. The agency cost theory of capital structure as well supports the idea of a firm having an optimal capital structure by its choice of capital

mix. It suggests that an optimal capital structure will be determined by minimizing the costs arising from conflicts between the parties involved.

2.3.4 The Static Trade-off Theory

The Static trade-off theory of capital structure (also referred to as the tax based theory) states that optimal capital structure is obtained where the net tax advantage of debt financing balances leverage related costs such as financial distress and bankruptcy, holding firm's assets and investment decisions constant (Baxter, 1967 and Attman, 1984). In view of this theory, issuing equity means moving away from the optimum and should therefore be considered unreasonable. According to Myers (1984) firms adopting this theory could be regarded as setting a target debt-to-value ratio with a gradual attempt to achieve it. However, he suggested that managers will be reluctant to issue equity if they feel it is undervalued in the market. The consequence is that investors perceive equity issues to only occur if equity is either fairly priced or overpriced. As a result investors tend to react negatively to an equity issue and management is reluctant to issue equity. This theory of capital structure supports the idea of a firm having a unique capital mix in order to maximize its market value taking into consideration both the bankruptcy costs and tax-shield advantage of debt capital. It predicts a positive relationship between a firm's choice of capital structure and its market value.

2.4 Empirical Review

Emori, E. G. & Ikenna D. N. (2015) conducted a study on the effect of capital structure on corporate performance in Nigeria using randomly selected companies. They selected twenty (20) companies operating in Nigeria and their study period was 2012 – 2013. The techniques of analysis include panel unit root test and the panel least squares regression. The result revealed that capital structure negatively influenced corporate performance. The study recommended that Nigerian companies should use debt as a source of finance sparingly and only when extremely necessary. Marcel, C. O. & Maria-Gorretti, E. O. (2019) carried a study on capital structure and firm value in Nigeria (Evidence from selected quoted firms). The study adopted long term debt and equity capital as independent variables of capital structure while Tobin Q was used as Proxy for firm value as the dependent variable. The population of the study was firms drawn from conglomerate and consumer goods sectors of Nigeria stock exchange for a period of nine (9) years 2007 – 2015. The techniques of analysis include descriptive statistics, correlation and ordinary least square (OLS) of multiple regression analysis. The study therefore, concluded that capital structure with regard to long-term debt was negatively but statistically significant to firm value, while equity capital was positively insignificant to firm value. The study recommended that firms should be more concerned with management of equity capital in business financing since it is more related to the value of the firm.

Ajayi, L. B. & Obisesan, O. G. (2020) conducted a study on impact of capital structure on firm performance in Nigeria for the period 2013 – 2017. The study considered the impact of some key macroeconomic variables (GDP and Inflation) on firm performance. The traditional theory of capital structure was employed to determine the significance of leverage and macroeconomic variables on firm's performance. A static panel analysis was used to achieve the objectives of the study. The study used fixed effect regression estimation model to establish a relationship between performance (proxied by return on investment) and leverage of the firms over a period of five years. The results provide strong evidence in support of the traditional theory of

capital structure which asserts that leverage is a significant determinant of firms' performance. The study found out that there was a significant negative relationship between leverage and performance. The study strongly recommended that firms should use more of equity than debt in financing their business activities, this is because in spite of the fact that the value of a business can be enhanced with debt capital, it gets to a point that it becomes detrimental.

Asen Ayange, Nwude, C. E., et al (2021) conducted a study on effect of Capital Structure on Firms Performance in Nigeria. The study used annual panel data for a sample of 15 quoted firms from diverse sectorial classification from 1999 – 2018. The study focused on non-financial firms. Results indicate that performance proxy by ROE, and Tobin's Q, significantly influence SDTA, SIZE, LDTA, and TDTA while ROA negatively influences LDTA DE, and TDTA.

Osasere, B. & Osagie, O. (2022), conducted a study on Capital Structure and Firms value in Nigeria: Does Industry Heterogeneity hold? The study was conducted to investigate the role of industry as a mediator on the capital structure – firm value nexus among listed oil/gas firms and Banking firms in the Nigeria Exchange Limited. Panel data spanning 21 years (2000 – 2020) was subjected to empirical analysis. Capital structure was measured using leverage ratio, equity ratio and interest expense while market based measure was used to measure firm value (Tobin's Q). The panel least square was used for data analysis along with other preliminary tests. Competition and technology were used as measures for industry factors while an industry dummy was used to capture industry differences. Their findings showed that leverage and equity had a significant positive relationship with firm's value while interest expense had a negative but significant relationship with firm's value. Leverage was found to change with the different industries and positively impacted firm's value. However, the findings showed that competition and technology did not change with industry thus these factors (technology & competition) are not significant in explaining possible changes in the capital structure of sampled firms. The study concluded that capital structure has a positive significance on firm's value while industry differences have a significant impact on this relationship. The study recommended that firm's should ensure that the proportion of leverage to equity do not grow to unsustainable levels to avoid the result of diminishing effect on firms value. Li and Islam (2019) demonstrated the importance of firm – specific and industry – specific factors in the leverage decision of Australian firms using the Ordinary least square method using data spanning 1999 – 2012. Findings showed that firm level factors varied between industries. Further findings showed that industry factors had an indirect and direct link with firm's capital structure.

3.0 Methodology

The population of this study consists of 173 listed domestic companies in the Nigerian Stock Exchange as at 31st December, 2022. The study sample consisted of eighteen (18) firms from nine (9) sectors of the Nigeria economy. The companies were selected using non-probability sampling method. The sectors are as follows: Beverage sector – 2 companies; Agricultural sector – 1 company; Engineering and Machinery sector – 1 company; Diversified Industries Sector – 3 companies ; Pharmaceutical sector – 1 company; Construction and building sector – 2 companies; Food producers and processors sector – 5 companies; Oil and gas sector – 2 companies; Transport sector – 2 companies; Transport sector – 1 company.

The study utilized secondary data which were obtained from the published annual financial statements and the Nigerian Stock Exchange fact book for the companies under study. This study covered a period of Ten (10) years 2012 – 2022. Panel data over this period was used to determine the impact of capital structure variables on firm value.

3.1 Estimation Technique & Procedure

The basic framework for panel data regression takes the forms:

$$Y_{it} = B_0 +$$

$$B_1 X_{it} + B_2 Z_{it} + u_i$$

In the above equation, the heterogeneity or individual effect is Z_{it} which may represent a constant term and a set of observable and unobservable variables (individual effect). When the individual effect Z_{it} contains only a constant term, OLS estimation provides a consistent and efficient estimates of the underlying parameters (Kyereboah-Coleman, 2007), but if Z_{it} is un-observable and correlated with X_{it} , then emerges the need to use other estimation method because OLS will give rise to biased and inconsistent estimation.

This study adopted the panel least squares models of either the Random effects model (Error component model) or the Fixed Effect Model (Least Squares Dummy) variable approach (LSDV) to analyse the effect of capital structure on firm performance in Nigeria. This study excluded the financial companies and the banking sector due to the uniqueness of their capital structure and the strict legal requirements for their financial choices. This study adopted Tobin's Q to measure a firm's performance and long Term Debt to the total asset (LTD/TA) as a measure of leverage. Firm size and firm Age are added as controlled variables and are considered to be an important determinant of a firm's profitability. The estimation procedure followed an array of pre-estimation tests, Panel estimation, and diagnostic tests. The unit root test was conducted to determine the data set stationarity.

3.2 Model Specification

The study investigated the impact of Industry heterogeneity in explaining the linkage between capital structure and firm value. For this purpose, this study adopted the model of Li and Islam (2019) whose study investigated the role of firm and industry specific factors as determinants of capital structure. Their model was given as:

$$\text{Leverage}_{it} = \alpha + B_1 \text{MB}_{it} - 1 + B_2 \text{TANG}_{it} - 1 + B_3 \text{PROFIT}_{it} - 1 + B_4 \text{SIZE}_{it} - 1 + \text{Industry effect} + \text{Year Effect} + \epsilon_i$$

Where

MB (Market Breath), TANG (Asset tangibility), PROFIT (Profitability) and SIZE (firm size) are all firm specific factors after controlling for industry and year effect. However, this present study modified the model to include leverage (Long Term Debt to the total asset), Equity and Interest expense. Firm size and firm Age were added as control variables of capital structure. Our model is thus given as

$$\text{Firm value} = f(\text{Capital structure}) \text{-----(1)}$$

$$\text{FIRM V} = f(\text{LTD/TA, EQCAP, INEXP, FIZE, FIGE}) \text{-----(2)}$$

$$\text{Tobin's Q}_{it} = f(\text{LTD/TA} + \text{EQCAP} + \text{INEXP} + \text{FIZE} + \text{FIGE}) + U_i \text{-----(3)}$$

Where

FIRM V = Firm Value Proxied by Tobin's Q.

LTD/TA = Long Term Debt to the total asset.

- EQCAP = Equity Capital
- INEXP = Interest expense
- FIZE = Firm Size
- FIGE = Firm Age
- Ui = error term

Re – specifying equation (3) into its econometric form, we have

$$TQ_{it} = \alpha o_{it} + \delta_1 LTD/TA_{it} + \delta_2 EQCAP_{it} + \delta_3 INEXP_{it} + U_{it} \text{ --- (4)}$$

We re-specify equation (4) to account for firm factors and we obtain

$$TQ_{it} = \alpha o_{it} + \delta_1 LTD/TA_{it} + \delta_2 EQCAP_{it} + \delta_3 INEXP_{it} + \delta_4 FSIZE_{it} + \delta_5 FAGE_{it} + U_{it} \text{ --- (5)}$$

Apriori expectation:

From the static trade-off theory, leverage and equity are expected to have a positive relationship with firm value. Interest expense is expected to be negative judging from the fact that increased interest expense can imply lower tax obligations given that interest is tax deductible, hence, higher value for the firm. However, higher interest rate will imply that the value of debt has risen which will increase the equity premium of the firm, hence lower value. Also, based on the dynamic trade-off theory, capital structure is expected to change given difference in firm and other related industry factors.

4.0 Results and Discussion

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev	Skewness	Kurtosis	P.value
TOBIN's Q	1.15	0.80	5.74	45.38	0.00
LTD/TA	0.89	0.61	7.58	78.2	0.00
EQCAP	0.17	0.25	-3.28	22.10	0.00
INEXP	6.97	1.14	-1.70	6.40	0.00
FSIZE	15.93	1.85	0.47	1.57	0.00
FAGE	38.06	20.32	1.64	6.96	0.00

Source: Author's computation (2024)

The characteristics of the dataset are presented in table 4.1. Findings showed that the average Market value (Tobin's Q) of the firms sampled is 1.15 with a standard deviation of 0.80. Leverage (LTD/TA) is observed to average at 0.89 indicating that the firms on an average were highly levered. The standard deviation is a little high showing that there was minimal deviation of leverage across the samples. Equity ratio is observed to be averaged at 0.17 indicating that 17% of shareholders fund was used to finance its asset. Equity ratio is found to be lower than debt usage. This confirms the Pecking order theory that asserts that companies will prefer to employ cheaper source of financing before using more expensive ones. Interest expense is observed to be high also and this stems from the high debt level of sampled firms. Firm's size has an average of 15.93 and standard deviation of 1.85. The Age of the firm has an average value of 38years and a standard deviation of 20years.

4.2 Regression Analysis

Different models were estimated to capture the impact of capital structure on firms' value by controlling for industry effect. Findings from table 4.2 show that the coefficient of leverage (LTD/TA) is positive (1.07) and significant (0.00). This shows that shocks in leverage will cause deviations in Tobin's Q by 1.07. The coefficient of leverage is observed to be dominantly positive and significant all through the models estimated. EQCAP is also observed to be dominantly positive (0.02) in all models although its significance is observed to vary. This also shows that a shock in EQCAP will cause a positive response from Tobin's Q by the strength of its co-efficient ceteris paribus. However, INEXP is observed to be predominantly negative given all models estimated and is found to be significant in all models. The significance of a firm's size on performance indicates that large firms earn higher returns compared to smaller firms, presumably as a result of diversification of investment and economies of scale. On the contrary, there is no significant relationship between firm's capital structure and firm's Age. This implies that the variable Firm's Age is not the major determinant of the firm's performance as Age of firms is significant and negative. This implies that the firms performance decrease as the firms increase in age.

Table 4.2 Regression Analysis (Tobin's Q as dependent variable)

Variables	Random Effect	Fixed Effect
Leverage	1.07 (0.00)**	1.01 (0.00)**
Equity	0.02 (0.83)	0.39 (0.00)**
Interest expense	-0.125 (0.00)**	-0.23 (0.00)**
Size	0.074 (0.06)**	0.745 (0.1786)**
Age	0.081 (0.007)	0.0748 (0.0320)**
Constant	1.05 (0.00)**	1.5 (0.00)**
R-sq	0.70	0.80
F-stat	192.5(0.00)	36.3 (0.00)
D-watson	1.46	1.63
Hausman Test	Chi ² = 0.86 (0.83)	

Source: Author's computation (2024). P-values are in parentheses () while ** and * signifies significance at the 1% level and 5% level respectively.

4.3 Short and long-run Heterogeneous Panel Based Analysis

The Pooled mean Estimator (Panel ARDL) is conducted to enhance the robustness of our findings. This particular method is chosen because of its ability to address endogeneity issues and providing a heterogeneous short-term parameters by allowing the short term parameters to vary while the long-run is constrained to be identical.

Finding showed that in the long run, all variables except EQCAP are significant. Specifically, leverage is observed to be positive and significant which confirms previous findings obtained in the Panel least square (PLS). EQCAP is equally found to be negative and not significant, thus indicating that EQCAP has no significant effect on firm's value. Interest expense is observed to be negative and significant which confirms the findings obtained from the PLS.

These findings support the fact that our result is robust to the econometric techniques used. However, the variable Age was dropped from the model because of its high collinear relationship with SIZE.

Table 4.3 Pooled Mean Group (PMG)

Method: ARDL			
Model selection criteria: AIC			
Model selected: ARDL 1, 1, 1, 1			
Long Run Equation			
	Coefficient	t-stat	P-value
INEXP	-0.06	-4.72	(0.00)**
EQCAP	-0.08	-0.64	0.51
LEV	1.57	17.61	(0.00)**
SIZE	0.47	2.91	(0.00)**
Short Run Equation			
COINTEQ 01	-0.19	-2.20	(0.00)**
D(INEXP)	-0.11	-0.94	0.32
D(EQCAP)	-0.14	-0.28	0.77
D(LEV)	0.21	0.54	0.55
D(SIZE)	-1.91	-1.48	0.14

Source: Author’s computation (2024). P-values are in parentheses () while ** and * signifies significance at the 1% level and 5% level respectively.

The short run estimate showed that 19% of past deviations are corrected in the current period. The error correction term is negative and significant which indicates that the variables equilibrate after minor deviation from short run shock. However, all variables are observed to possess their long run properties although they are observed to be insignificant.

Table 4.4: The general pattern in the capital structure of quoted firms in Nigeria.

Capital structure		Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Valid	Equity only	20	22.22	22.22	22.22
	Debt only	0	0	0	22.22
	Debt & Equity	70	77.78	77.78	100
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Source: The Nigerian Stock Exchange fact book, (2010)

4.4 Discussion

Table 4.4 seems to provide an answer to the question which seeks to determine the general pattern in the capital structure of quoted firms in Nigeria. From the table that was sourced from the Nigerian stock exchange fact book, (2010), it was observed that capital structure sourced from Equity only was 22.22%, Debt only 0% while Debt and Equity combined was 77.78%. Hence, no firm can run a business successfully on debt only, and

relying on Equity alone affect capacity of firms in reaching optimal performance in their business. Long-term debt was found to be the major determinant of firm's value because it is significant in this analysis. This is consistent with the findings of Ogbulu & Emeni (2012), Antwi et al (2012), Myers and Majluf's (1984).

This study and the previous studies revealed that market imperfections present in the real world such as bankruptcy cost, agency costs, gains from leverage – induced tax shields and information asymmetries have all contributed to support long-term debt as the major determinant of firm's value because it is significant in sustaining firms value. This study revealed that in an emerging economy like Nigeria, equity capital is irrelevant to the value of a firm. This is in line with the findings of Ogbulu & Emeni (2012). It is also in agreement with the claims put forward by the proponents of the Pecking order theory. It is also in line with the capital structure irrelevancy theory of Modigliani and Miller (1958), which states that equity capital is unrelated to firm value.

5.0 Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Summary of Findings

Based on this study, there are many factors that can influence a firm's choice of capital structure. Some of these factors include availability and benefits of a particular source of capital, profitability, cost of capital, risks, shareholders opinions, the level of development of the Nigerian stock market, firm's sizes, shareholders' fund, etc.

A firm's market value is positively and significantly influenced by its choice of capital structure. This is the major reason why optimal capital structure is sought for to enhance optimum business performance.

Capital structure changes given industry heterogeneity. Industry has a significant impact in mediating the relationship between firms value and capital structure. The findings of this study demonstrate that leverage and equity changes in respect to industry which shows that firms operating in different industries will most often have different capital structure. Hence, the capital structure of firms is not static but changes given different factors operating in the firm and industry level. This is in line with the study of Li and Islam (2019), Mackay and Philips (2005) whose studies found that industry heterogeneity has a significance role in the capital structure of firms.

5.2 Conclusion

This study has examined the impact of capital structure and the influence of heterogeneous factors on firms' value taking into cognizance eighteen (18) firms from nine (9) sectors of the Nigerian economy. Based on the findings of this study, we can conclusively state that capital structure is positively related with firm's value, and industry differences have a significant impact on this relationship. Since there are many theories on capital structure, firms should have financial policy on their capital structure based on the prevailing circumstances within their business. Again, firms in Nigeria should strive to optimize their capital structure by an appropriate mix of debt-equity capital. They should always strike a balance between their choice of capital structures and the resultant effects on shareholders risks and returns and the cost of capital.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions arising from the analysis of data, this study recommends as follows:

- a) Firms, should ensure that the proportion of leverage to equity do not grow to unsustainable levels to avoid the result of diminishing effect on firms value./ They are strongly advised to always compare the marginal benefit of using long-term-debt before concluding on using it in financing their operations. This is because as shown by this work, long term debt impacts positively on firm's value.
- b) Firms should stop using more of Equity capital in business financing since it is unrelated to the value of a firm because the tax benefit which is obtained for the relevance of capital structure in relation to firm's value is offset by the fact that shareholders pay more tax than bondholders.
- c) Too much leverage is not good for Nigerian companies. This is due to the fact that Nigeria is a developing country. Nigerian companies should use debt as a source of finance sparingly and only when extremely necessary. This is because despite the fact that the value of a business can be enhanced through debt, a point is reached when further increase in debt becomes detrimental. As such, each firm should establish its optimum debt-equity ratio that will maximize its value.

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